

Synthesis of some *m*-(Phthalimidoalkyl)-4-substituted-cinnamoylbenzanilides and Study of their Hypoglycemic Activities

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In view of the biological importance of anilides¹, some *m*-(phthalimidoalkyl)-(4-substituted-cinnamoyl)benzanilides have been synthesised with a view to examine their hypoglycemic activities. The present communication reports the synthesis of title compounds and evaluation of their biological activities.

Phthalimidoalkylbenzoic acids (2) were prepared by refluxing *N*-hydroxyalkyl phthalimides (1) and benzoic acid in ethanol in the presence of sulphuric acid. The corresponding acid chlorides (3) were obtained by treating the compounds with PCl₅, which were then condensed with acetophenone and anhydrous potassium carbonate to get 4. The benzanilides (4) were condensed with aromatic aldehyde and trimethylamine to yield the titled compounds (5).

Results and Discussion

Only compounds 5f, h and i exhibited moderate hypoglycemic activity, i.e. 17, 10 and 14% (average max. reduction of body sugar, mg%) respectively, whereas others showed negligible activity.

The behavioural changes of albino rats as a result of hypoglycemic condition was studied by adopting the reported procedure⁶. The animals administered compounds 5f, h and i reveal a low ambulation and grooming comparing to the control one (Table 1). But so far as learning is concerned, reverse phenomenon is observed. As hypoglycemic condition is associated with decrease in cell metabolism hampering learning and activity of the organisms, the animals administered 5f, h and i showed maximum reduction in body sugar as obtained on the present case, which agrees with the views of the earlier workers⁷. Data on mean scores of different groups on each indices are incorporated in Table 1.

A study of the structure-activity relationship of different compounds suggest that *m*-phthalimidoalkyl group is mainly responsible for hypoglycemic activity and ethyl group is more effective than methyl, and also lengthening of the alkyl chain improves the activity.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Tlc was carried out using solvent system benzene-acetone (80 : 20).

m-Phthalimidoalkylbenzoic acids (2) : To benzoic acid (0.4 mol) dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) was added a hot solution of *N*-hydroxymethyl/ethyl phthalimide (1; 0.4 ml) in ethanol^{2,3} slowly with constant stirring followed by con-

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5

Compd. no.	n	R	M.p. °C	Indices		
				Ambulation		Stimulus discrimination
5a	1	4-NH ₂	165	20.8	3.4	20.0
b	1	4-OH	126	28.0	4.6	18.0
c	1	4-OC ₆ H ₅	93	21.2	4.0	19.0
d	1	4-NO ₂	182	22.0	4.2	18.6
e	1	2-COOH	105	—	—	—
f	2	4-NH ₂	164	17.0	2.0	22.0
g	2	4-OH	120	21.0	4.0	20.0
h	2	4-OC ₆ H ₅	162	18.6	3.2	20.8
i	2	4-NO ₂	175	19.0	3.4	20.4
j	2	2-COOH	112	—	—	—
		Control		35.0	5.0	15.0

centrated H₂SO₄ (5 drops) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. On cooling, the separated solid was dried and crystallised from acetone. Similar methods were applied with other compounds (Table I) : *m*-phthalimido-methylbenzoic acid, m.p. 228–30° (lit.³ 229°); *m*-phthalimidoethylbenzoic acid, 219° (lit.³ 215°).

m-Phthalimidoalkylbenzoyl chloride (3) : *m*-Phthalimidomethyl/ethylbenzoic acid and phosphorus pentachloride (0.25 ml) were dissolved in dry benzene. The solution was refluxed on a water-bath for 2.5 h under anhydrous conditions and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to yield the product.

m-Phthalimidoalkyl-*p*-acetylbenzanilides (4) : A mixture of 3 (0.2 ml), *p*-aminoacetophenone (0.2 ml) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (2.2 g) dissolved in CCl₄ (100 ml), was refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath under anhydrous condition. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue was washed with 10% NaHCO₃ solution till effervescence ceased. The crude product was crystallised from ethanol : *m*-phthalimidoethyl-*p*-acetybenzanilide (55%), m.p. 161–63° (Found : N, 6.7. C₂₅H₂₀N₂O₄ calcd. for : N, 6.79%); *m*-phthalimidoethyl-*p*-acetybenzanilide (60%), m.p. 158° (Found : N, 7.2. C₂₄H₁₈N₂O₄ calcd. for : N, 6.9%).

m-(Phthalimidoalkyl)-4-substitued-cinnamoyl)benzanilides (5) : To 4 (0.1 mol) dissolved in absolute ethanol (45.0 ml) was added a solution of the aromatic aldehyde⁴ (0.1 mol) in ethanol (45 ml) followed by triethylamine (2 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for

about 5 h, then ethanol distilled off and the residue treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). The compounds (yields 49–62%) were dried and crystallised from acetone.

Hypoglycemic activity : The compounds were screened for their hypoglycemic activity in albino rats of either sex by measuring the changes in blood glucose as well as behaviour. The fasting blood sugar was collected from the rats before and after administration of the test compounds, emulsified with gum tragacanth (a non-hypoglycemic compound) and the glucose content in the blood was measured following the reported procedure⁵.

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